

Abstract

Functional and Structural Brain Changes During Acupuncture Therapy of Migraine.

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Abstract

Introduction: Migraine without aura is a common and debilitating neurological condition characterised by recurrent attacks of intense pain and a significant impact on quality of life. Acupuncture, recognised by the World Health Organization as a therapeutic option for migraine prophylaxis, has shown promising clinical results. However, the neural mechanisms underlying its analgesic effects remain poorly understood. The ACU-BRAIN study was designed to bridge this gap by using advanced neuroimaging techniques to investigate how acupuncture modulates the microstructural organisation of white matter and the functional connectivity of brain networks involved in pain. Understanding these mechanisms may contribute to the development of neural biomarkers and the refinement of personalised therapeutic approaches.

Methodology: The ACU-BRAIN study is a randomised, sham-controlled, single-blind trial involving 40 adult patients diagnosed with migraine without aura. Participants were divided into two groups: real acupuncture and sham acupuncture, receiving five sessions of standardised acupuncture spaced 15 days apart. Clinical and neuroimaging assessments were performed during the first and last sessions, both before and after the intervention. Imaging techniques included:

- Diffusion Tensor Imaging (DTI): For the microstructural analysis of white matter.
- Resting-state fMRI (rs-fMRI): To investigate local brain connectivity and functional networks.

Clinical variables included pain intensity (VAS), functional impact (HIT-6), Patient Global Impression of Change (PGIC), and the number of migraine days per month. This combination allows for a parallel evaluation of neural changes and clinical progression.

Results: The ACU-BRAIN study results show that after the treatment sessions, the real acupuncture group presented significant differences in white matter microstructure and functional brain connectivity compared to the sham group. Specifically:

1. **Structural Changes:** Higher Fractional Anisotropy accompanied by lower Mean Diffusivity was identified, suggesting adaptive processes of microstructural reorganisation throughout the treatment.
2. **Functional Changes:** An increase in Regional Homogeneity was observed, alongside greater expressivity of the Default Mode Network (DMN). This indicates enhanced local synchronisation of neuronal activity and potential functional reorganisation of networks related to pain perception and modulation.
3. **Integration of Findings:** When analysed together, these structural and functional patterns are consistent with adaptive processes and neural reorganisation associated with the therapeutic effect of acupuncture.
4. **Correlation with Clinical Improvement:** These neural modifications correlated positively with clinical recovery indicators, including:
 - Reduction in the number of migraine days per month.
 - Decrease in pain intensity (VAS).
 - Significant improvement in functional impact scores (HIT-6).

Conclusions: The findings suggest the presence of neural biomarkers capable of explaining and potentially predicting the therapeutic response to acupuncture, reinforcing its potential as a modulator of brain circuits related to pain. The safety profile was favourable: adverse events were mild and

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transient (such as site discomfort, minor bruising, or vasovagal reactions), and the non-contrast MRI remained safe for all participants.

Overall, the ACU-BRAIN study provides evidence that acupuncture is not only associated with a reduction in clinical symptoms but also correlates with detectable changes in microstructural organisation and brain network functioning. These results support acupuncture as a mechanism-based therapeutic strategy.

Limitations: The study has several limitations. The relatively small sample size (40 participants) reduces statistical power and may limit the generalisability of the results. As a single-centre study, extrapolation to other populations is restricted. Furthermore, the two-month follow-up duration does not allow for an assessment of long-term persistence. Finally, while sham acupuncture is a strong methodological control, it can still produce minimal neurophysiological responses, potentially attenuating the differences between groups.

Keywords: Migraine; Acupuncture; Neuroimaging; DTI; rs-fMRI; Brain Plasticity.

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